

New Antiplasmodial Derivative from a Dimerization of Chloroquinolin radical cations of Amodiaquin

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ABSTRACT

A new derivative **1** has been synthesized by dimerization of radical cations from 4-[3'- diethyl amino methyl-4'-hydroxyanilino]-7-Chloroquinolin known as amodiaquin. The synthesized compound has been characterized using proton, carbon-13, 2D-COSY, 2D-HSQC Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data and by Mass spectrometry. The evaluation of its *in vivo* antiplasmodial activities above The NMRI mouses shows that the derivative **1** is most active than its analogue amodiaquin. The derivative **1** shows a parasitemia rate of 0.20% against *Plasmodium bergeri* administered to the NMRI mouses, whereas the parasitemia rate of amodiaquin amount to 47% under the same conditions. This higher activity of the derivative **1** confirms the pharmacophore character of the chloroquinolin part in the antiplasmodial activity.

Keywords: Amodiaquin, New derivative, higher *in vivo* antiplasmodial activities

INTRODUCTION

Malaria, the most important tropical disease caused by 4 different species of plasmodial parasites, is estimated to kill between 1.5 and 2.7 millions people each year, with over 300 millions currently infected¹. Eighty per cent of cases are registered in sub-Saharan Africa, where malaria concerns in the majority young children under five years of age and pregnant women². In order to fight malaria, different compounds with different activities have been brought on the market, among them chloroquin, amodiaquin, quin... Thus, a number of antiplasmodial compounds have been developed, but the emergence of antiplasmodial drugs resistance has been increasing³. Amodiaquin, for instance, can be used nowadays for the treatment of malaria only in combination with artesunate. It is an aminoquinolin, which is only active against the chloroquinoreistant parasites⁴. Chloroquin has been declared ineffective against the *plasmodium* by WHO^{5,6,8}. The parasites develop also more and more resistance in the presence of quinine, the first effective drug used to control malaria^{7,8}. All these remain a great obstacle in the control of malaria in the regions where this disease is endemic².

Owing to the increasing resistance to these antiplasmodial compounds, we have thought that instead of a simply abandoning of these drugs, which have shown their effects during several years, to proceed if possible via structural modifications of these antiplasmodial drugs by synthesis and to subject the obtained products to *in vivo* antiplasmodial screening above the NMRI mouses⁹. It is in this frame that we have synthesized the compound **1** from amodiaquin. The synthesis of 4-(4'-chloroquinolinyl)-7-chloroquinolin through a dimerization of both 7-chloroquinolin radical cations induced by sunlight accompanied of the *in vivo* evaluation of its antiplasmodial activities above the NMRI mouses expressed by the parasitemia rate make up the important contributions of this work.

Synthesis of 4-(4'-chloroquinolinyl)-7-chloroquinolin **1**

The synthesis of amodiaquin derivative **1** was carried out by a strong acid catalyzed dimerization of both 7-chloroquinolin radical cations induced by sunlight at room temperature during 12h. The

formation of radicals was possible, because the amodiaquin absorbs also into the visible range (section between 400 and 500 nm)^{10,11}. The addition of NaOH to pH 8 led up to get the derivative **1** as brown crystals in good yield.

The chemical equation can be summarized in this manner as illustrated in the scheme I:

Scheme I

EXPERIMENTAL PART

TLC: aluminium sheets silica gel (60 F254).

¹H- and ¹³C-NMR spectra: Bruker AC-250 (250 and 63MHz, resp.), tetramethylsilane and CD₃SOCD₃ with respect to TMS as internal references; δ in ppm and J in Hz. MS: HCT-spectrometer, manual injection.

4-(4'-Chloroquinolinyl)-7-chloroquinolin (**1**).

To a stirred mixture of 9.2ml (220.2mmol) concentrated nitric acid and 9.2ml (172.6mmol) concentrated sulfuric acid at cold (the temperature should not exceed 10°C) was added 10g (25.6mmol) of amodiaquin.2H₂O by portion of 1g all five minutes. The resulting solution was stirred for 12h by sunlight at room temperature. A solution of 5N NaOH was then dropwise added until pH 8. The solid residue was filtered, washed with distilled water until pH 7 of waste water. The product was at last dried during a week: **1** was isolated (2.5g, 60%) as brown crystals. ¹H-

NMR: Table 1. ¹³C-NMR: Table 2. Mass spectrum: Table 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical results

The progress of the reaction for getting amodiaquin derivative **1** has been monitored by thin layer chromatography. Amodiaquin shows a R_f value of 0.48, whereas its derivative **1** has a R_f value of 0.65 with methanol as eluent. This led us up to say that there has been effectively a reaction which has given a product whose the structure is fully supported by ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR, 2D-COSY and 2D-HSQC Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data. These analyses were completed by the mass spectrometry.

Table 1. ¹H-NMR Data (CD₃SOCD₃) of the amodiaquin derivative **1** at 250 MHz; δ in ppm and J in Hz, internal standard TMS

NH	11.77
H-C(2) and H-C(7')	8.07
H-C(6) and H-C(3')	7.92
H-C(8) and H-C(5')	7.58
H-C(3) and H-C(8')	7.32
H-C(5) and H-C(2')	6.05

J(2,3) and J(7',8')	8.5
J(6,5) and J(3',2')	6.0
J(3,2) and J(8',7')	8.5
J(5,6) and J(2',3')	7.0

Table 2. ¹³C-NMR Data (CD₃SOCD₃) of the amodiaquin derivative **1** at 63MHz; δ in ppm, internal standard TMS

C(7) and C(4')	176.79
C(10) and C(10')	141.25
C(6) and C(3')	140.42
C(4) and C(1')	136.68
C(2) and C(7')	127.79
C(9) and C(9')	124.85
C(3) and C(8')	123.91
C(8) and C(5')	117.86
C(5) and C(2')	109.78

Table 3. MS-Data of the amodiaquin derivative **1**

MS: 325(4, M⁺), 307(94), 279(26), 264(51), 253(66), 210(13), 198(62), 184(100), 160(57), 134(9), 110(38)

Fig.1 2D-COSY of the derivative **1**

Fig.2 2D-HSQC of the derivative **1**

The comparison of ¹H-NMR spectra of the amodiaquin and its derivative **1** shows the absence of the protons of 4-(3'-diethyl aminomethyl-4'-hydroxyanilino) substituents in the product. The low-field region of the ¹H-NMR spectrum of the derivative **1** reveals 6 peaks between 12 and 6 ppm which are assigned to the chloroquinolin part. The chemical shifts at 6.05 ppm, 7.32 ppm, 7.58 ppm, 7.92 ppm and 8.07 ppm are respectively assigned to the protons(5), (3), (8), (6) and (2). Taking into account the mass spectrum data of the derivative **1**, it observes that the M⁺ peak appears at m/z 325. This mass for the derivative **1** can be explained by a dimerization reaction of the both chloroquinolin parts. A further large band at 11.77 ppm in the ¹H-spectrum of the derivative **1** can be understood by the protonation of both nitrogens of the chloroquinolin units by H₂O contained in the NMR solvent through the following reaction:

The peak of H₂O in ¹H-NMR spectrum can be observed at 3.34 ppm. In aqueous organic solvents, pyridin is more nucleophilic or basic than H₂O, and this nucleophilic of pyridin can be compared with that one of 1-aminobenzene¹². That the concerned protons come from water in d₆-DMSO is to observe through a crosspeak in the 2D-COSY spectrum(Fig.1).Referring to the M⁺ peak at m/z 325 and to the dimerization reaction, the integration of each peak in the ¹H-NMR spectrum corresponds then to two protons.

The ¹H-NMR spectrum was completed by ¹³C-NMR spectrum. In this latter, we observe the presence of 9 peaks, that correspond to 9 carbons of the chloroquinolin unit. The correlation between the hydrogens peaks and the carbons peaks is to find in the 2D-HSQC spectrum (Fig. 2). The particularity that we have in our case is that the carbons (7) and (4') linked to the chloratom appear in very low-field region (176.79 ppm) of the ¹³C-NMR spectrum. This can be explained in the fact that the protonated derivative **1** in NMR solvent d₆-DMSO knows a resonance due to a mesomeric

donating effect of the chloratom fixed to the aromatic nucleus of the quinolin and to the positive charge on the nitrogen atom. It results a push-pull system that causes a hyperconjugation in the following manner:

This hyperconjugation gets an effect on the $^{13}\text{C-NMR}^{13}$. Indeed, the second mesomeric form with double bonds between the positive chloratom and the carbons (7) and (4') shows that these latter behave as a carbon of the carbonyl group. For this reason, these carbons of quinolin unit appear in very low-field region (176.79 ppm), and the sp^2 methine carbons (2) and (7') near of the nitrogen shift around to 127.8 ppm in $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectrum like in an indol group¹⁴. The push-pull system due to a mesomeric donating effect of the chloratom and the positive charge on the nitrogen atom of pyridine favours the balance to the second mesomeric form on the right. The mass spectrometry analysis of the derivative **1** shows a M^+ peak at m/z 325; what corresponds to the mass of 4-(4'-chloroquinolinyl)-7-chloroquinolin.

All this leads us up to say that there has been an acid catalyzed dimerization of both 7-chloroquinolin radical cations induced by sunlight. The formation of radical cations was possible, because amodiaquin absorbs also into the visible range between 400 and 500nm^{10,11}.

After the determination of the structure of the synthesized product **1**, the *in vivo* antiplasmodial activities of the product **1** have been evaluated in relation to that one of the amodiaquin in order to complete this work.

In vivo antiplasmodial Tests

4-(4'-Chloroquinolinyl)-7-chloroquinolin **1** has been evaluated for its antiplasmodial activities above the NMRI mice grown at the Institut National de Recherches Biomedicales/ Kinshasa, DRC and infected with *plasmodium bergeri*. Different doses have been administered to the different mice, and the parasitemia has been followed during six days of treatment.

At the maximal concentration (0.99mmol/l) for the amodiaquin and its derivative **1**, this last compound **1** showed an antiplasmodial activity more than amodiaquin (0.20% vs 47% of parasitemia rate), which was used as the reference substance.

CONCLUSION

The design of a new antiplasmodial agent and its synthesis through an acid catalyzed dimerization of radical cations induced by

sunlight make up important contributions of this work.

The biological tests show that amodiaquin derivative **1** exhibit *in vivo* higher activity than amodiaquin against the plasmodial agents. This higher activity of the derivative **1** confirms the pharmacophore character of the chloroquinolin unit in the antiplasmodial activity.

Considering these results, we can assert that amodiaquin, which has been declared ineffective against the *plasmodium* by WHO, can be used again by structural modification through a good oriented synthesis.

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